

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

Deliverable D8.1: Project Management Plan

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ACRONYMS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
CMT	Coordination and Management Team
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DG	Directorate-General
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
FSS	micro-Farm Structure Surveys
GA	Grant Agreement
GAs	General Assembly
HBS	Household Budget Surveys
LP	Lead Partner
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PMO	Project Management Officer
PMP	Project Management Plan
PR	Periodic Report
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RMS	Risk Management Strategy
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SILC	Statistics on Income and Living Conditions
SJOS	Safe and Just Operating Space
SO	Specific Objective
SPAB	Scientific and Policy Advisory Board
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Work Package
WR	Wageningen Research

1. SUMMARY

1.1. Project Summary

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is the European Union's (EU) flagship policy for supporting the agricultural sector, ensuring food security, and safeguarding rural development while it is also a key tool for reaching the objectives of the European Green Deal, including the Farm to Fork and the Biodiversity Strategy. With these policy strategies, the EU aims for more sustainable food systems. Effectively supporting the policy impact assessment in this new context is a great challenge for the existing quantitative modelling tools as it requires them to substantially enhance the thematic coverage to comprehensively address all the components of the European Green Deal and ensure consistency with the monitoring systems in place.

ACT4CAP27 responds to this challenge by *(i) enhancing the analytical capacity of the key policy tools* (CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD) used by the European Commission to assess short-term and long-term policy impacts on EU's agri-food systems and *(ii) providing evidence-based knowledge* supporting analysis for the design of *agri-food policies post 2027*.

ACT4CAP27 develops a consistent, interdisciplinary methodological framework to operationalise and quantify relevant aspects of the EU agri-food system and related policies post 2027 and their economic, social (including health), environmental and climate sustainability impacts. Act4CAP27 addresses the main shortcomings of current modelling tools with its Act4CAP27 Modular Toolbox for EU Food System Modelling which provides a basis for innovation by creating a collaborative space and a modular model infrastructure for the whole EU agri-food research community and beyond. The Act4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform establishes an appropriate and inclusive engagement with stakeholders to co-create, communicate, and disseminate Act4CAP27 research results.

ACT4CAP27 launches an Interactive Roadmap for guiding EU, national and regional policy makers weigh up policy objectives and choices to move the EU food system towards more sustainable outcomes.

1.2. Executive Summary

Work Package (WP) 8 management and coordination for ACT4CAP27 aims to deliver a well-managed project to the European Commission (EC) and to all stakeholders. Coordinator WR is developing D8.1 – this Project Management Plan (PMP), which outlines the key operational management procedures, controlling processes to be used, the project policies and rules and the overall management approach. WR will provide regular updates and ensure its implementation throughout the project.

2. INTRODUCTION

This Project Management Plan (PMP) is based on the PM2 template of the European Commission (EC, 2018). The plan documents the selected approach for implementing the project goals. It also highlights the key controlling processes to be used, the project policies and rules and the overall management approach. The plan becomes the basis for managing the project throughout its lifecycle and is an important point of reference for all project partners and stakeholders. The plan is kept up to date throughout the time span of the project.

The Project Partners involved in WP8 are all partners responsible for leading a WP (WR, LSHTM, SLU, IIASA, Thünen Institute, UPM, ECORYS) and POS, which partner has shared responsibilities with ECORYS in Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE). The WP Leaders together form the Executive Board (EB) of the ACT4CAP27 project.

These partners, with WR in the lead, are responsible for the project's activities and progress against task timetables, ensuring adherence with the Description of the Action (DoA) in the Grant Agreement (EC, 2024), this PMP, including communication and organisation mechanisms described herein and in adherence with the Consortium Agreement (CA, 2024). This is being realised by ensuring milestones and deliverables are achieved on time, monitoring, assessing and managing potential risks and problems as they arise. The management and coordination of the project depends on four main entities.

These are: 1) the Coordination and Management Team (CMT), 2) the General Assembly (GAs), 3) the EB and 4) the Scientific and Policy Advisory Board (SPAB).

This PMP provides the ACT4CAP27 partners a set of practical guidelines for the execution of the project. The plan is prepared by the CMT at Wageningen Research (WR) and was submitted to the EB, including the Scientific Coordinator (SC) / WP8 leader, for validation.

3. PROJECT OVERVIEW

3.1. Objectives

The overall objective of the ACT4CAP27 project is to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community. The project adopts a comprehensive food system approach, focusing on building analytical capacity for the quantitative assessment of the impacts of upcoming agri-food policies on the economic, social (including health), environmental, and climate sustainability of food systems. This effort is directed towards providing continuous support for ex-ante analyses of EU agri-food policies post-2027, aligning with the objectives of the European Green Deal (EGD).

ACT4CAP27 advances beyond the state of art by focusing on:

- DESIGNING a conceptual data and modelling framework to operationalize and better understand the determinants and indicators for an improved EU food system performance and ASSESSING policy impact.
- Developing an enhanced modular MODELLING Toolbox to quantify the transition to a sustainable EU food system and its contribution to societal goals.
- SAFEGUARDING the uptake and update of the integrated and modular toolbox and community building.
- Building a PLATFORM for stakeholder interaction and dialogues – at different stages of the project.

3.2. The ACT4CAP27 Project Facts

Coordinator	WR
Timing	60 months: 1 March 2024- 28 February 2029
Total budget	5,434,000 EUR
Partners (13)	WR, Thünen Institute, EuroCARE, IIASA, SLU, UPM, WU, PNU, UNIROMA3, ECORYS, POS, LSHTM, JRC

The (confidential) list of all partner information and people involved in the project (in Excel format) is available and regularly being updated on the ACT4CAP27 project's environment in Sharepoint.

3.3. Methodological Framework

The methodological framework of the ACT4CAP project consists of the following three pillars which are connected by thematic and modelling work and the stakeholder community: 1) Designing and assessing WP1 and 6); 2) Modelling (WP2 and 3); 3) Safeguarding (WP 4 and 5) and dissemination and stakeholder Platform (WP7) .

Pillar 1 Designing and assessing

The first specific objective (SO-1) is to DESIGN a conceptual data and modelling framework to operationalize and better understand the determinants and indicators for an improved EU food system performance and ASSESS policy impact. The target outcome of pillar 1 is the definition and

operationalization of EU system performance and the generation of empirical evidence of linkages and cause-effect relations.

Pillar 2: Modelling

The second specific objective (SO-2) is to develop an enhanced modular MODELLING TOOLBOX to quantify the transition to a sustainable EU food system and its contribution to societal goals. To this end, novel dataset modules will be developed in the field of economic, social, environmental and climate sustainability covering input use, sustainability indicators, and policies. The target outcome of Pillar 2 is to expand the scope of the model modelling capabilities into domains that are currently not included or underdeveloped.

Pillar 3: Safeguarding

The third specific objective (SO-3) is to SAFEGUARD the uptake and update of the integrated ACT4CAP27 toolbox and community building. To this end 1) a portal with created dataset modules and scenario results will be build and provided to preserve knowledge after the project, and 2), analytical capacities will be built up in the modelling community. The target outcome is to accelerate the transfer of modelling and analytical knowledge and experience via capacity building.

Dissemination and stakeholder Platform

The fourth specific objective (SO-4) is to develop an ACT4CAP27 PLATFORM for stakeholder interaction and dialogues at different stages of the project. O.7.1. is to maintain a continuous dialogue with the EC and stakeholders and other key actors. O.7.2. is to maximise the visibility of the project and ensure project results reach end-users in effective ways. One of the target outcomes of WP7 is to develop an active and operational stakeholder platform. Figure 1 (see below) represents the workflow of the project.

Figure 1 Research strategy

3.4. Key Outcomes

The four key outcomes to develop in the ACT4CAP project are:

- A methodological framework that operationalizes and quantifies impacts of upcoming agri-food policies on the economic, social, environmental and climate sustainability of the EU agri-food system;
- An integrated and modular modelling toolbox;
- A platform for stakeholder engagement and capacity building;
- An interactive roadmap for policy guidance.

4. LIST OF ACT4CAP27 WORK PACKAGES, MILESTONES AND DELIVERABLES

WP 8 (WR) will ensure that the milestones and deliverables of all WPs are achieved and delivered on time. To enable this, specific management tools and mechanisms will be used to monitor progress, incorporating traffic-light signalling to indicate progress in completing the project deliverables. Different colours will be used to indicate if deliverables are: 1) completed, 2) within 2 months of delivery date, 3) if the delivery is outstanding or 4) delivery grossly overdue.

4.1. List of Work Packages

In Table 1 the different WPs and their lead partners (LPs) are described.

Table 1 Work Packages of the ACT4CAP27 project

WP no	Work Package Title	LP	LP no	Person months	Start month	End month
1	Conceptual framework and analytical tools gap analysis	WR	1	26	1	24
2	Coverage of economic, social, environmental and climate sustainability of food systems	LSHTM	12	86	1	36
3	Model structures for representation of agro-food systems and policies	SLU	5	124	12	48
4	ACT4CAP27 data and model portal	IIASA	4	40	12	60
5	Modelling infrastructure and capacity building	UPM	6	38	6	60
6	Assessments of EU agri-food policies post 2027	Thuenen	2	91	24	60
7	Stakeholder engagement and dissemination	ECORYS	10	47	1	60
8	Management and Coordination	WR	1	34	1	60
9	Ethics requirements	WR	1	0	1	60

4.2. List of Milestones

The project's milestones are described in Table 2.

Table 2 Milestones of the ACT4CAP27 project

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related WPs	Due date	Means of verification
M1	Conceptual framework food system indicators	1, 2	M9	Conceptual framework and sustainable food system dimensions\ indicators will be discussed and validated in 1st Stakeholder meeting.(M8).
M2	CAP post 27 policy scenario studies	1, 5	M24	Outputs of 2nd Stakeholder meeting (M20) will be used.

M3	ACT4CAP27 medium and long term baselines	5	M36	Baseline with alternative futures, validated by stakeholders (3rd meeting, M32) and made available for internal\external access.
M4	Modular ACT4CAP27 modelling toolbox	4, 5	M42	ITC infrastructure for open-source and cloud-based access to toolbox and baseline up and running.
M5	ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap	6	M60	Web-based Interactive Roadmap is launched, the input of 4th Stakeholder meeting (M44) will be used.
M6	Capacity building	5	M60	Three training sessions organized by the consortium: coordination of partners' training and capacity building activities.
M7	Final conference	7	M60	Final conference proceeding.

4.3. List of Deliverables

Table 3 includes the list of deliverables with the formal delivery dates of uploads on the EC portal for funding and tenders. This list is accessible in Excel format to all ACT4CAP27 partners via SharePoint. All the intermediate outputs and agreed internal project management deadlines are also mentioned in this list.

Table 3 Deliverables of the ACT4CAP27 project

WP No	D-WP No	D No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead	Type	DISS Level	Due Date
WP1	D1.1	D1	An operational food systems framework for analysing sustainable outcomes	An operational food systems framework for analysing sustainable outcomes, consisting of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An integrated analytical framework that addresses sustainability dimensions simultaneously • A list of indicators that can be used to measure sustainability at different scales 	WR	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP1	D1.2	D2	Report on CAP post 2027 policies, modelling gaps, and identification of scenarios	Report on CAP post 2027 policies, modelling gaps and identification of scenarios for analysing sustainable food systems.	Thuenen	R	PU	28 Feb 2026
WP2	D2.1	D3	A health assessment module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	Health assessment module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis.	LSHTM	R	PU	28 Feb 2027

WP2	D2.2	D4	Environmental assessment modules: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	Environmental assessment modules: documentation on data, implementation and analysis.	IIASA	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP2	D2.3	D5	Socio-economic assessment module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	Socio-economic assessment module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis.	WR	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP3	D3.1	D6	Global input module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	Global input module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis.	SLU	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP3	D3.2	D7	EU module of consumer preference shifts: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	Consumer preference module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis.	Thuenen	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP3	D3.3	D8	Network model of supply chains: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	Network model of supply chains: documentation on data, implementation and analysis.	UPM	R	PU	29 Feb 2028
WP3	D3.4	D9	CAP and GD policies module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	CAP and GD policies module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis.	Thuenen	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP4	D4.1	D10	Report on technical guidance and examples for data processing and modularization	Report on Technical guidance and worked examples for data processing (T4.1) and modularization in the context of the Computational Framework (T4.2).	IIASA	R	PU	31 May 2025
WP4	D4.2	D11	Report on Prototype of the Database (T4.1) and Scenario Explorer	Report on Prototype of the Database (T4.1) and Scenario Explorer (T4.3).	IIASA	R	PU	28 Feb 2026
WP4	D4.3	D12	Report on Prototype of the Computational Framework	Report on Prototype of the Computational Framework (T4.2).	IIASA	R	PU	31 Aug 2027

WP4	D4.4	D13	The ACT4CAP27 Portal for user-friendly stakeholder engagement	The ACT4CAP27 Portal for user-friendly stakeholder engagement.	IIASA	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP5	D5.1	D14	Model infrastructure to bring model-based evidence closer to policy making	Model infrastructure to bring model-based evidence closer to policymaking.	SLU	R	PU	29 Feb 2028
WP5	D5.2	D15	Documentation on analytical tools to design and assess CAP policies post 2027	Documentation on analytical tools to design and assess CAP policies post 2027.	EuroCare	R	PU	29 Feb 2028
WP5	D5.3	D16	ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling	ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Modelling.	SLU	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP5	D5.4	D17	Capacity building activities	Capacity building activities.	UPM	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP6	D6.1	D18	Fast track results of all tasks	Fast track results of all tasks.	Thuenen	R	PU	31 Aug 2028
WP6	D6.2	D19	ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap for transition to a sustainable EU Food System	ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap for transition to a sustainable EU Food System.	WR	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP7	D7.1	D20	Stakeholder engagement strategy plan and annual reports	Stakeholder engagement strategy plan (M6) and annual reports (M13, 25, 37, 49 and 60, ECORYS).	ECORYS	R	PU	31 Aug 2024
WP7	D7.2	D21	Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan and Reporting	Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan, and Reporting (M6, 18, 36, 48, 60, POS).	POS	R	PU	31 Aug 2024

WP7	D7.3	D22	Exploitation plan	Exploitation Plan.	POS	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP7	D7.4	D23	Project website	Project website	POS	R	PU	31 Aug 2024
WP7	D7.5	D24	Policy brief 1	Policy brief 1	POS	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP7	D7.6	D25	Policy brief 2	Policy brief 2	POS	R	PU	31 Aug 2025
WP7	D7.7	D26	Policy brief 3	Policy brief 3	POS	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP7	D7.8	D27	Policy brief 4	Policy brief 4	POS	R	PU	29 Feb 2028
WP7	D7.9	D28	Policy brief 5	Policy brief 5	POS	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP8	D8.1	D29	Project Management Plan	Project Management Plan	WR	R	PU	31 July 2024
WP8	D8.2	D30	Data Management Plan	Data Management Plan	WR	DMP	PU	31 Aug 2024
WP8	D8.3	D31	Report on cumulative expenditure year 1	Report on cumulative expenditure year 1.	WR	R	SEN	28 Feb 2025
WP8	D8.4	D32	Report on cumulative expenditure year 2	Report on cumulative expenditure year 2.	WR	R	SEN	28 Feb 2026
WP8	D8.5	D33	Report on cumulative expenditure year 3	Report on cumulative expenditure year 3.	WR	R	SEN	28 Feb 2027

WP8	D8.6	D35	Report on cumulative expenditure year 4	Report on cumulative expenditure year 4	WR	R	SEN	29 Feb 2028
WP8	D8.7	D34	Report on cumulative expenditure year 5	Report on cumulative expenditure year 5	WR	R	SEN	28 Feb 2029
WP8	D8.8	D41	Progress Report	Progress Report	WR	R	SEN	31 Aug 2026
	D9.1	D36	H – Requirement No. 1	Response to comments in the Ethical Summary Report (ESR) on the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants	WR	ETHICS	SEN	31 Aug. 2024
	D9.2	D37	POPD – Requirement No. 2	Response to comments in the ESR on safeguarding the rights of data subjects or the processing of genetic, biometric and/or health data	WR	ETHICS	SEN	31 Aug 2024
	D9.3	D38	NEC – Requirement No. 3	Response to comments in the ESR on how fair benefit-sharing arrangements with stakeholders from low and lower-middle income countries are ensured.	WR	ETHICS	SEN	31 Aug 2024
	D9.4	D39	AI – Requirement No. 4	Response to comments in the ESR on the use of AI system/technology	WR	ETHICS	SEN	31 Aug 2024
WP9	D9.5	D40	OEI – Requirement No. 5 – Ethics Advisor Appointment	Response to the advise in the ESR to appoint an external independent Ethics Advisor and the tasks of this Advisor, including the requirement to report at the end of each reporting period.	WR	ETHICS	SEN	31 Aug 2024

5. PROJECT MANAGEMENT OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the ACT4CAP27 project management (WP8) is to deliver a well-managed project to the EC and all project stakeholders, through the specific objectives:

O8.1 To ensure project research and innovation activities are managed and coordinated effectively.

O8.2 To ensure effective and efficient financial and administrative management of the project

O8.3 To ensure FAIR data management and high quality of the deliverables.

O8.4 To ensure synergies and linkages with other relevant projects.

5.1. Description of the Project Management Work

WP8 consists of the following four tasks:

1. The project governance, the coordination and strategic decision-making, led by WR, with support from the EB (the WP leaders and POS), the GA and the SPAB. The CMT provides the governance structure for the ACT4CAP27 project, including the overall management of all project tasks, contractual and financial matters, adjustments, preparation, and maintenance of the GA and the CA, based on the DESCA 2020 format. The CMT moderates strategic decisions, resolves conflicts and communicates with the EC. Regular exchanges between the CMT and WP leaders via MS Teams, ensure timely identification and resolution of issues that may jeopardise objectives and deadlines.

2. Administrative and financial project management. The CMT handles the day-to-day administrative and financial tasks, monitors project activities and progress, takes corrective actions when necessary, provides interim reports as per contractual agreements, ensures that milestones and deliverables are met on time, monitors income and expenditures, distributes funds to partners, acts as the primary contact for partners, and organises project meetings including the kick-off, annual GA meetings and the final conference.

3. Data management and quality control. WR has delivered the DMP (D8.2) in M6, which ensures implementation in line with FAIR data principles. Quality control of project deliverables is ensured through the preparation and implementation of procedures outlined in the CA.

4. Establishing connections and collaborations with related projects. ACT4CAP27 actively engages with projects on similar topics, particularly the “HORIZON-CL6-2021-Governance-01-12: EU agriculture within a safe and just operating space and planetary boundaries (the BrightSpace project)”, “HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-13: Modelling land use and land management in the context of climate change” (the LAMASUS project), as well as H2020 projects (including SUPPORT, BATMODEL, MindStep, AGRICORE, BESTMAP, CONSOLE, Contract and EFFEC) and new Horizon Europe projects. Where possible, WR prepares back-to-back project meetings, organises joint conference workshops and sets up collaborative research projects with these projects. To organise this, WR has made an inventory of relevant related

projects.

WP8 will provide the following deliverables and reports:

- D8.1 Project Management Plan (M5, WR);
- D8.2 Data Management Plan (M6, WR);
- Periodic report 1 (M18);
- Periodic report 2 (M42);
- Final Periodic report 3 (M60).

6. PROJECT ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

In the following section, the roles of pivotal actors in the project are described alongside with the responsibilities, expectations, rights and duties of each participant related to the project. The management of the collaboration between all partners has been defined in detail in the CA, according to the Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement (DESCA) model.

6.1. Organisational structure and decision making

The management and coordination of the project depend on four main entities (the CMT, GAs, EB and SPAB).

6.1.1. The coordination and Management Team (CMT)

The CMT is based at Wageningen Economic Research (part of WR) and is responsible for the day-to-day coordination of the project. The CMT is 'the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the parties and associated partners and the granting authority. The coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the GA and the CA (ACT4CAP27 Consortium Agreement, 2024, p.11). The team consists of the project coordinator (PC), the scientific coordinator (SC), the project manager (PM) and the project management officer (PMO). The PC will be the pivot for all contact with DG Research and act as an intermediary between the EC and the consortium. The CMT is authorised to execute the project management, reports and is accountable to the EB, which in turn will report and be accountable to the GAs. Corporate WUR resources are also available to assist with legal and contractual work and with invoicing and cost statement preparation. The CMT will also be responsible for the overall data management of the project (described in D8.2).

Table 4 Overview of the Coordination and Management Team of the ACT4CAP27 project

Name	Role
Siemen van Berkum	Project Coordinator
Hans van Meijl	Scientific Coordinator
Marjan Vooijs	Project Management Officer

6.1.2. The General Assembly (GAs)

The GAs will be the ultimate decision-making body of the project and will meet annually. The GAs is composed of one representative from each partner organisation and is responsible for the strategic direction and overall governance of the project. The GAs meeting will be chaired by the PC and/or the PM. The responsibilities of the GAs are described in the CA (2024), signed by all project partners. To ensure an effective remit and given the object of ensuring the project's maximal impact, the GAs will:

- analyse performance indicators and all other relevant information provided by the EB;
- take into account the analysis on the evolution of the context in which the project is carried out, notably, scientific, legal, societal and economic aspects.

GAs meetings are held annually, preferably as part of the annual project meeting, unless the project requires intermediate meetings. In that case, GAs meetings will be initiated by the coordinator or at the request of a majority (more than 50%) of GAs members. The GAs makes decisions by simple majority voting, with a casting vote for the coordinator in the case of equal votes. Each partner shall be entitled to send one voting representative to the GAs. Any partner representative may nominate a substitute member from his/her own organisation to represent them as proxy. Decisions of the GAs on the matters described below, will be taken by consensus where possible, otherwise they require that at least two-thirds of the project partners vote in favor of a particular proposition. Where possible, decisions will be based on consensus. The CA (2024) provides the procedures, in particular if no consensus is reached. If necessary, decisions based on votes in a meeting require a two-third majority of the votes cast, under the condition that two third of the members are present in the meeting. As described in the CA (2024): in case a decision will be taken without a meeting, 51% of all partners have to agree.

Specifically, the GAs approves matters relating to:

1) content, finances and intellectual property rights:

a) proposals for amendments of the GA;

b) proposals for changes to Annexes of the GA, to be agreed by the Granting Authority;

c) changes to the CA;

d) proposals for modifications or withdrawal of Background in Attachment 1 of the CA (Background);

2) the evolution of the consortium:

a) entry of a new party or associated partner to the project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new party or associated partner;

b) withdrawal of a party or associated partner from the project and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal;

c) identification of a breach by a party or associated partner of its obligations under the CA or the GA;

d) declaration of a party or associated partner to be a defaulting party;

e) remedies to be performed by a defaulting party;

f) termination of a defaulting party's participation in the consortium and measures related thereto;

g) proposal to the granting authority for a change of the PC;

h) proposal to the granting authority for suspension of all or part of the project;

i) proposal to the granting authority for termination of the project and the CA.

In the remaining cases, the authority to make decisions is delegated to the CMT.

6.1.3. The Executive Board (EB)

The EB is the second main management body of the project, next to the CMT. It is responsible for effective implementation of and adherence to the CA and the GA, ensuring that all milestones and deliverables are achieved. The EB is advised by the SPAB. It facilitates the interdisciplinary focus in the project. It prepares and carries out decisions of the GAs regarding strategy, progress, project amendments, exchanges, collaboration and gender, ethical and political issues. Chaired by the PC, the EB comprises of all WP leaders (from WR, LSHTM, Thünen, IIASA, UPM, Ecorys) and POS in addition. The EB interacts on a monthly basis through Teams meetings and in person at least every 12 months at project annual meetings. The EB prepares the decisions to be taken by the GAs (e.g. concerning the description of work, budget and EC contribution allocation) and ensures that decisions are properly implemented. The EB takes decisions by simple majority, voting with a casting vote by the PC in the case of a tied vote.

Concerning general project coordination and management, the EB will specifically:

1. support the CMT in fulfilling obligations towards the EC;
2. ensure that all work meets the functional requirements;
3. monitor the overall performance relating to the allocated work, deliverables and other activities to be provided or carried out by the project partners under the contract and the implementation plan (Part B of the GA), as well as informing the GAs of any non-performance;
4. review and propose the GA budget transfers in accordance with the contract and the implementation plan;
5. propose changes in work sharing, budget and partners to the GAs;
6. make proposals to the project partners (other than a defaulting partner) to serve notices on a defaulting partner and to assign the defaulting partner's tasks to specific entities;
7. agree on press releases and joint publications by the project partners with regard to the project;
8. agree on procedures and policies for dissemination of knowledge from the project, which is not to be used by the project partners;
9. provide regular information to the project partners on all project activities, distribution of any documents and exchange of information with respect to the project activities to and between the WPs and the project partners concerned;
10. propose the decision to the GAs to suspend all or part of the project, or to terminate all or part of the contract, including the modalities of such termination with respect to ongoing activities, or propose a decision regarding a request by the PC to the EC to terminate the participation of one or more project partners in the consortium;
11. inform the SPAB in order to enable them to advise the CMT about:
 - a. strategic project issues;
 - b. the scientific foundation;

- c. the scientific reviewing process;
- d. the development in their surroundings.

Concerning scientific coordination the EB will specifically:

- 12. ensure high scientific quality;
- 13. review each deliverable to ensure that it meets the objectives according to the deliverable;
- 14. ensure open access of publications.

6.1.4. The Scientific and Policy Advisory Board (SPAB)

The SPAB:

provides information to the ACT4CAP27 project about relevant developments external to the project;

provides an overview and advisory role over the implementation strategies and activities of the project;

meets bi-annually and serves as an advisory body - a discussion platform to consult different aspects of the project;

serves as a powerful dissemination channel.

The SPAB is composed of relevant and influential stakeholders (see Table 4). The participation of the SPAB members has been approved by the EB.

The SPAB's role is to:

- advise the EB on changes in scientific, societal, policy and consumer priorities that may impact the project's objectives and expected impacts;

act as a sounding board regarding how the impact of the project can be maximised and on ethical matters;

propose changes to the direction of the project in line with stakeholder and end-user priorities for maximising the exploitation and benefits of the project;

review the progress of the project annually;

support the dissemination of the project's results in their respective institutions and related organisations.

The SPAB will have access to documents of the project. After each annual meeting, the SPAB will formulate a statement on the progress of the project and a list of recommendations. The SPAB can be expanded during the project to include other relevant actors. Table 4 lists the SPAB members.

Table 5 Scientific and Policy Advisory Board members

External expert	Affiliation	Organisation
Sophie Helaine	Head of Unit Policy Performance (AGRI.A.3)	DG AGRI
Fanny Le Gloux	Research Program Officer, Research and Innovation Unit F2	DG AGRI
Herve Guyomard	Director of Research	INRA, Rennes
Harald Grethe (tbc)	Professor Agricultural Economics	Humboldt University, Berlin

7. RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

A coherent Risk Management Strategy (RMS) will be applied according to the ISO 21500 Guidance, by identifying, assessing, treating, monitoring and control risks during the course of the project. Risk management is a continuous process that will be undertaken throughout the time span of the project.

Reaching the proposed objectives of the ACT4CAP27 project, is both challenging and complex. In order to realise such an ambitious project successfully, potential risks need to be anticipated up-front and precautionary measures outlined that can be applied immediately in case of problems and thereby allow an undisturbed continuation of the project for reaching its goals. Key risks and proposed mitigation strategies are identified for the project.

Risks will be carefully managed according to a defined process, including risk planning, identification, analysis, mitigation measures in response to risks, monitoring, generally applying principles of a Deming: plan, do, check, act cycle. During the project execution, each risk will be assessed in terms of probability and its impact. The management support team will contact the main contact person per risk to gather information on the risks and will update the PC on the status, if required. Project management will store risks and mitigation updates, including their evaluation, in the risk register on Sharepoint. In case necessary, risk management will be scheduled in the EB meetings to take the necessary measures. The identified mitigation actions will be executed when necessary and its effect appropriately evaluated. The focus is on risks with a high probability of occurrence, in combination with a high impact on the project result if the risk occurs.

The risk register includes at least information on (**bold** according to the information needed for the EC):

- **Risk description and number**
- Mitigation measure
- Responsibility (WP)
- Contact person
- Impact
- Probability
- **Mitigation measures applied**
- **Occurance of the risk**
- **Comments: if the risk-mitigation measures couldn't be applied, an explanation why**
- Action by (time)
- Action when (time)

As defined in the GA, several risks and risk-mitigation measures have been defined at the submission of the proposal. The list of critical risks for implementation and the list of barriers in achieving expected impacts and mitigation measures to overcome them as described in the GA, are included in Annex 1 of the GA (see also Annex to this document). This serves as a baseline for the project's risk management. If any unforeseen risks occur during the project, we will

monitor and manage these similarly as for critical risks. Actions to overcome barriers which influence project impact, are elaborated in deliverable D7.2 (D21): Communication, Dissemination, Impact Strategy and Plan (WP7). To ensure that these barriers are mitigated, there is close collaboration between WP8 and WP7 to monitor and enhance maximal project impact. If barriers become project risks, these will be managed similarly.

8. QUALITY CONTROL PROCEDURES

8.1. Common Framework and indicator system for quality management and model validation

The ACT4CAP27 modular toolbox (WP2-3), together with WP4 (ACT4CAP27 data and model portal) will link a variety of models and dataset modules designed for specific uses. Because of the large variety of tools and their tasks, validation requires a model-specific approach, including issues related to the consistency of data, computational processes and output indicators. These procedures need to account for upcoming policy requirements in terms of sectoral challenges, policy measures and the broad policy objectives for the whole EU food system. The aim is to support validation across these three WPs and to provide a thorough guideline and identification of indicators, to assess model validity on different scales (the common framework and indicator system for model validation). This framework aims to ensure, e.g., that 10 tools are suitable to investigate relevant policy measures; 2) key indicators of interest are covered, and 3) valid results are provided. The resulting framework is considered as a mean of quality management.

8.2. Quality management of all project Deliverables

Quality control of project deliverables will be ensured by preparing and implementing procedures to underpin the delivery of scientific and technical aspects of the project. The quality assurance of the deliverables is summarised in the following four steps:

1. The WP leader is responsible for finalising all WP deliverables in time and within budget. The WP leader will deliver the first review, by acting as a first-step of checking and approving the deliverable within the WP;
2. A WP leader from another partner organisation will deliver the peer review. This peer reviewer will be jointly appointed by the EB;
3. The CMT provides the final check on the deliverable;
4. The CMT takes care of submitting all deliverables to the portal.

Table 6 Description of the procedural actions and durations for quality assurance of the deliverables

Review process of ACT4CAP27 deliverables	Time/week
First review of the deliverable by the WP leader	Week 1
Peer review by another WP leader, from another partner organization	Week 2
Processing remarks by the (main) authors and check by the WP leader	Week 3
Final checks by the CMT	Week 4
Deliverable sent to the CMT for submission via the EC Portal	Week 5

Table 7 Responsibilities of the quality management of all deliverables described in more detail

Role	Responsibility
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Task leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assigns the lead author in charge of the deliverable. - Involves all contributors to the deliverables. - Sets up delivery time plans and deadlines. - Follows the formatting of the document template provided.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is responsible for the technical content of the deliverable and its clear communication, in written form. - Ensures timely preparation of the deliverable to meet the deadline.
WP leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Checks the technical quality and that the deliverable strictly follows the formatting template. - Checks the consistency of all deliverables within the WP. - Monitors the overall planning and timely submission of all deliverables in the WP. - Reviews (1) the deliverable.
Other project partner – other WP leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reviews (2) the deliverable with emphasis on the methodological approach, structure of the document and quality, provides comments and proposes corrections/edits for improvement for consistency over WPs, within the project.
CMT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitors the overall submission process. - Conducts a final consistency and quality check to finalise the deliverables. - Submits the approved deliverable to the EC.
SPAB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assesses the quality of key deliverables and checks on procedures in order for the level of the quality to be realised.

9. OTHER PROJECT MANAGEMENT TOPICS

9.1. External communication management

The findings and results of ACT4CAP27 are packaged to reach, engage, and address the end-user needs and will be widely shared with all relevant actors. Resources will be mobilized to ensure that the project remains visible to society. Therefore, a communication and stakeholder engagement strategy is developed to map and reach key actors and to link the project to the relevant communication channels and platforms in WP7. See Deliverable D7.2 (D21): Communication, Dissemination, Impact Strategy and Plan and Reporting (WP7). The exploitation and dissemination plan will be updated throughout the project to ensure that the results can be properly exploited by the targeted end-users. The plan will be further defined for each of the project's outputs: i) the specific area, ii) the potential users, iii) the dissemination strategy, iv) the potential uses and v) the timing. This plan will also contain guidelines on the sustainability of the project results, in order to preserve and develop these for the end users, beyond the duration of the project. The stakeholder engagement strategy is being designed to maximize impact and carefully tailor materials and tools to the specific needs of the target audiences. A list of key contacts in each partner country will be compiled to disseminate the information to a wider audience and key actors.

9.2. Internal communication management

Collaboration during the ACT4CAP27 project is supported by a Microsoft Teams and Microsoft Sharepoint environment to which all project participants have access. All 'channels' in MS Teams and document folders in MS Sharepoint are accessible to all project partners. Having all project communications and shared documents in one place, benefits team collaboration and enhances the quality of project activities and documents.

The main driver for using MS Teams is that project participants can work on shared documents simultaneously. A second driver is that for WUR it is not allowed to use Google drive, as company policy for security reasons. A third driver is that MS Teams is now widely used and we expect that scattered communication can be avoided by adopting to this main stream system. Instead of circulating project documents (including deliverables) to the consortium by email, the responsible partner will upload it to the relevant MS Teams 'channel' and notify the partners through email, with a link to the uploaded document.

A project email address will be used for sharing information and addressing the day-to-day business of the project: act4cap27@wur.nl. All questions related to financial administration and project management can be sent to this email address.

Regular project meetings form the basis for good consortium cooperation and a sound working progress. A number of (internal) meetings will be held during the course of the project. See Table 7 in which the type of meetings, the organizers, participants, frequency and form (online/physical location) are indicated. Agendas will be provided by the organizer of the meeting. An Action List, as a summary of the meeting outcomes, will be jointly elaborated by

the participants of the meetings. There can be a deviation of the frequency in meetings, in consultation with the project manager.

Table 8 Meetings of the ACT4CAP27 project

Meeting	Chair	Participants	Frequency	Location
GAs Annual Meeting	PC	Representatives of all partners	Yearly	In person
CMT	PM	CMT	Bi-weekly	Online/in person
EB	PC	WP leaders and co leaders	Monthly	Online
WP tasks	WP leader/task leader	Partners involved in the tasks	As agreed	Online
SPAB	SC	SPAB members and WP leaders	Twice per year	Online/in person

10. PERIODIC REPORTING

As outlined in Article 21.1 of the Grant Agreement, the coordinator is responsible for continuous reporting on behalf of all consortium partners regarding the progress of deliverables, milestones, critical risks, etc. This reporting is conducted through Continuous Reporting on the EC Funding and Tenders Portal.

Apart from continuous reporting, Periodic Reporting entails submission of project progress and financial statements at specific intervals to ensure accountability and compliance.

The project is divided in 3 Periodic Reports (PR):

1. PR 1 - M01-M18;
2. PR 2 - M19-M42;
3. Final PR 3 – M43-M60.

Each periodic report will be finalized and submitted by the coordinator within 60 days after the end of the reporting period. It consists of detailed technical reports and financial statements.

Technical report

The technical report consists of two parts:

Part A comprises a publishable summary and continuous reporting data entered into the EC Funding & Tenders Portal.

Part B, a PDF document uploaded by the coordinator, includes a narrative detailing work per WP and partner, along with deviations and the use of resources.

WP leaders are responsible for preparing individual reports covering WP progress, deliverables, milestones in compliance with the GA. The CMT has final responsibility for drafting the periodic report, including the WP progress reports, summarizing the project status (KPIs), monitor inconsistencies and taking care of the final submission.

Financial report

Each project partner has to prepare their organisation's financial statements. They will be prepared and submitted to the coordinator for inclusion in the financial report of the PR, using the EC Funding and Tenders Portal.

Every partner is obliged to check its financial reporting procedures to comply to the requirements of the EC and to avoid common errors. Detailed instructions on the financial reporting will be distributed before the reporting by the project coordination team, who will also cross-check the financial statements and request additional clarification if required. Any deviations in the use of resources will be added to the Technical Report – Part B.

Guidance and Templates

To prepare for Periodic Reporting, the coordinator issues clear guidance, three months before the end of the reporting period. This guidance includes detailed instructions and planning via

email, along with a structured set of templates based on the Technical Parts A and B. These resources are distributed to all WP leaders and consortium partners to facilitate their input.

Responsibilities

All partners engage with the coordinator for any input and queries during the reporting process. The coordinator oversees submission to the EC Funding & Tenders Portal. After submission, the European Research Executive Agency (REA) reviews the reports within 90 days, allowing for adjustments and revisions.

Review

After submission, a project review session will be scheduled, during which the coordinator and WP leaders will present the project's progress. The Project Officer and external reviewers will offer feedback and recommendations on the report and associated deliverables.

Payments

Interim and final payments are subject to the submission and approval of mandatory deliverables and periodic reports.

11. APPROPRIATENESS OF THE ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE AND DECISION-MAKING MECHANISMS

The organisational structure of ACT4CAP27 (see Table 9) is designed to ensure that the project is effectively managed with the different decision-making bodies covering the diverse levels of management needed. The decision-making mechanisms are well distributed across partners who possess the necessary experience and institutional infrastructure to cope with the demands of such a multi-actor project.

Table 9 Management level, decision-making bodies and their roles

Level of management	Decision making	Role
Strategic management	GAs	Strategic orientation Analyse performance indicators and all other relevant information provided by the EB
	EB	Operational management of all project activities
	CMT	Communication with the EC, monitoring of technical and scientific progress, risk management
Administrative, financial and risk management	CMT	Communication with the EC, monitoring of technical and scientific progress, risk management, both at strategic and operational level
	CMT	Day to day monitoring of progress, risk management, administrative and financial management and quality control
WP Management	WP Leaders	Leadership, coordination, monitoring, risk management and delivery of partner activities in their respective WPs Provision of effective cooperation at the interface of their WPs with others and for working cooperatively with other WP leaders and management bodies (e.g. GAs, CMT)

The quality control procedures and the distribution of responsibilities among the partners, as outlined in the previous chapters, will help to organise the ACT4CAP27 project in an effective manner and is based on and consistent with experience in other Horizon projects (MIND STEP, 2020; Smart Agri Hubs, 2019; BrightSpace (2022), SUPPORT, 2023). However, it should be noted that the procedures and internal organisation of the ACT4CAP2027 project will be revised throughout the duration of the project and may undergo some revision, should certain protocols prove to be inefficient or impractical.

12. GENDER ISSUES

The quality control procedures and the distribution of responsibilities among the partners, as outlined in the previous chapters, will help to organise the ACT4CAP27 project in an effective manner and is based on and consistent with experience in other Horizon projects (MIND STEP, 2020; Smart Agri Hubs, 2019; BrightSpace, 2022; SUPPORT, 2023). However, it should be noted that the procedures and internal organisation of the ACT4CAP27 project will be revised throughout the duration of the project and may undergo some revision, should certain protocols prove to be inefficient or impractical.

13. ETHICAL CLEARANCE

The Ethic Summary Report (2023) concludes that ACT4CAP27 serious and/or complex ethics issues raises due to the involvement of human participants, personal data, non-EU countries and Artificial Intelligence, and finds that these issues are not sufficiently acknowledged in the Ethics Self-Assessment. Therefore, an external independent Ethics Advisor must be appointed by month 3, with expertise on safety issues, data protection, and compliance with the EU ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI.

The ethics advisor/board should advise the consortium on:

- Recruitment of volunteers as data subjects.
- Collection and proper handling of personal data and with a focus on health related issues and individual consumer behavior.
- Transfer of personal data from/to the EU to non-EU countries and their processing abroad.
- Use of AI in the form of machine learning and secure compliance with the EU Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI.
- Safety of activities carried out in Ukraine.

A report by the Ethics Advisor must be submitted by as a deliverable by month 6 and then at the end of each reporting period.

The report reaches its conclusion based on the following considerations

- a. Human participants will be involved in a range of activities, such as surveys, choice experiments and lab (-in-the-field) experiments, to elicit consumer preferences and willingness to pay for innovative technologies and products (e.g. artificial meat). Vulnerable people might be involved, as the project will analyse food purchasing power, labour demand, employment, and income inequality at household level (P.30-31, Task 2.3). The behaviour of people will be studied to improve the prediction of consume patterns and potential behaviour shifting mechanisms developed (P.13, 31, Task 2.3). There are inconsistencies between Part A and Part B, as lab (in the field) experiments are described only in Part A.
- b. The project will collect personal data through various activities (e.g. surveys on the socio-economic status of individual farms and households). The behaviour of people will

be studied and potential behaviour shifting mechanisms developed (P.13, 31, Task 2.3), thus the activities may involve profiling of people. The project will process sensitive personal data such as health (diet-related diseases, mortality), social (food security, employment, inequality) (P.2, 5, 30 Task 2.1) and sex and age (P.12, 16) and will use secondary data sources which may contain personal data (P.30, 32 WP2, WP3). Despite the measures to protect personal data (e.g. pseudonymization), individuals may be re-identified. The project will collect geo-location data, whenever the applied methods permit to attribute a probability of each farm to belong to different spatial units (parcels identified from satellite imagery) (Task 2.2). WP2 will develop satellite modules to enable a comprehensive sustainability (environmental, health, social, and socio-economic) impact assessment of the food system.

- c. On Non-EU countries, the Ethics Summary Report notes that the transfer of EU personal data to the UK is a potential ethics issue, and with respect to Ukraine, data will be collected and probably transferred to other countries for processing and analysis. Also, there are safety risks due to the war. The ethics self-assessment identified ethics issues related to non-EU countries, however the applicants have not addressed these issues sufficiently, e.g. Ukraine has not been recognised as a country which belongs to the group of lower-middle income countries. Also, due to the geopolitical situation in Ukraine, there are safety concerns regarding the individuals involved in planned activities.
- d. The project involves identification of patterns in remotely sensed data and the use of machine learning techniques (both activities considered AI). It is unclear if there will be any interaction with humans. These AI activities are only acknowledged in part A. The robustness of the machine learning element is insufficiently explained.

We will follow the report's recommendation and appoint an Ethics advisor to address the identified issues. However, we would like to make the following comments in advance on the points raised in the Ethics Summary Report. The Report notes that ACT4CAP27 activities include primary (personal) data collection of consumer behaviour and farm data (parcels via satellite imagery). This finding is based on what is written in the section on the Ethics dimension of the project; the Ethics Summary Report then makes some links to activities in WP2 and 3. However, the Report also points out inconsistencies in the proposal because activities involving the collection of personal data, choice and lab (in the field) experiments are mentioned in part A (in the Ethics Self-assessment section) but not in part B. Personal data collection, choice experiments and/or data on parcel use are also not part of the activities in WP2 and 3, nor of any of the other WPs. Also, machine learning and/or Artificial Intelligence (AI) are not used in this project: these methods are not mentioned in the description of the WP activities. From the latter it should be clear that the models and databases are improved and strengthened by supplementing them with existing data from publicly available sources or from EU (Eurostat) sources where data are depersonalised.

How then can this inconsistency be explained? In retrospect, we can conclude that we were sloppy in drafting the Ethics paragraph. In the process of proposal writing, we planned some data activities that were no longer considered realistic in the final stage of proposal writing, and did not end up in the activities of the WPs. Unfortunately, the Ethics paragraph was neglected to be adjusted correctly, when we submitted the proposal.

As stated, we support the recommendation that the Ethics advisor address the concerns raised in the Report and trust that the advisor's report will quickly lead to the conclusion that the project is marked as 'ethics ready'.

14. REFERENCES

ACT4CAP27 Consortium Agreement AP Version 3, 24 January 2024. Based on DESCA-Model Consortium Agreement fro Horizon Europe version 1, December 2021.

Ethics Summary Report (2023) Associated with document Ref. Ares(2023)4948124 - 17/07/2023

European Commission (2024). Grant Agreement: project 101134874 – ACT4CAP27. HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01. European Research Executive Agency (REA), Associated with document Ref. Ares(2023)7543882 - 07/11/2023

ANNEX 1: CRITICAL RISKS AND BARRIERS FOR IMPLEMENTATION

A.1 Critical Risks for Implementation

As defined in the GA, several risks and risk-mitigation measures have been defined at the submission of the proposal (see Table 10).

Table 10 Critical risks for implementation

Risk number	Description	Work Package No(s)	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	Delivery delays in one WP cause delays in dependent WPs (Low/Low)	WP2, WP4, WP3, WP5, WP1, WP6	The WPs within the project are structured in a way such that most critical components from different tasks are developed within the same WP to minimize this risk. Strict and regular monitoring by WP leaders will flag potential delays in delivery or unsuitable quality at an early stage.
2	Low end users' engagement in the stakeholder engagement activities (Low/High)	WP7	The project involves recognised research organisations with good connection to stakeholders and established networks. Additional outreach activities will be implemented if needed, and continuous feedback-based improvement guaranteed. Workshops organisation will remain flexible and defined according to real needs to promote end user interest.
3	Covid or a new pandemic prevents international travel (Low/Low)	WP7	Virtual communication will be organised, mobilising a range of media tools. The workshops and final conference can be converted to online/hybrid format if required.
4	Continuation of military invasion of RF into Ukraine, which limits the holding events with stakeholders (Average/Low)	WP2, WP3, WP6	Virtual communication will be organized, mobilising a range of media tools. The workshops and the final conference can be converted to online. Planning events will be organized, taking the probability of air raid alerts into account
5	Mobilization of research oriject participants to fulfill the planned obligation (Low/High)	WP2, WP3, WP6	Scientific contingents are interchangeable within the framework of the project. The workload for other project team members can be increased.
6	Issues in the implementation of simulation protocols, exchange of data and integration of models in the toolbox (Low/High)	WP2, WP4, WP3, WP5, WP6	Precise definition of inputs, outputs, required formats and resolution by the modelling teams is key and guidelines will be provided at early stages. Regular meetings will be organised to co-develop and clarify simulation protocols and quality checks foreseen.

7	Delayed access to critical datasets generated outside the consortium such as FADN data. (Medium/ Medium)	WP2, WP4, WP3	Most of the datasets used are either directly produced by one of the partners or within one of their projects. If data cannot be accessed, owners of the data will be contacted to set up a usage agreement, alternatives will be found, or the data will be produced within the project if feasible.
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A.2 Barriers in achieving expected impacts and mitigation measures to overcome them

Next to risks and risk-mitigating measures at the submission of the proposal, barriers in achieving expected impacts and mitigation measure to overcome them have been defined (see Table 11).

Table 11 Barriers in achieving expected impacts and mitigation measures to overcome them

Barriers	Mitigation measures
Political support for Green Deal objectives and, hence, demand for sustainable food systems assessments diminishes	Platform and communication will target wide group of stakeholders, including other groups that support Green Deal objectives (e.g. NGOs), which ensures outcomes are disseminated in case political support is dwindling.
Rotation of EU policy makers in relevant DGs connected to ACT4CAP27	Engagement of policy makers in the ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform is critical to align models in the toolbox with lead user requirements, and to establish effective and sustained working relationships with EU policy makers.
Limited interest by policymakers to engage with ACT4CAP27.	Implementation of ACT4CAP27 dissemination and communication activities combined with active exploitation of existing networks and contacts will support policymaker interest and engagement. A user friendly ACT4CAP27 Portal provides relevant information on policy implementation and possible impacts to regional user communities and decision makers.
Geopolitical, economic or societal crises may impact policy priorities	ACT4CAP27 develops an integrated view on agricultural policies to identify best-practice ‘no-regret’ policies that deliver benefits on an exhaustive set of economic and environmental indicators.

Possessio

<https://act4cap27.eu>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

<http://tinyurl.com/ACT4CAP27OpenAIRE>